

EFFECTIVENESS OF PROBLEM TEACHING METHODS IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

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Abstract: The article describes the problem-based learning used in the teaching of all subjects today and the effectiveness of applying problem-solving situations from chemistry to the teaching process.

Key words: problem-based learning, problem-based learning technologies, problem, problem-based situation, muscular (alken).

Problem learning technologies are based on the activation and acceleration of the student's activities. The basis of problem learning technology is that a person's thinking begins with solving a problem situation, as well as the fact that he has the ability to identify, research and solve problems. Problematic education is of serious importance in the cultivation of creative thinking and creative abilities of students.

In the problematic teaching of chemistry, the teacher remains the leader of the educational process, but it is necessary that he get out of the role of a person who informs knowledge, as in a traditional group, and be an observer, developing the mental actions of students. Corrects errors, explains the places of suspicion of tasks. The process of carrying out problematic teaching, which is organized in chemistry, itself was a problem " " what training should a teacher undergo in order for them to successfully master the problematic teaching of chemistry?"raises a very important issue.

The teacher who teaches chemistry must explain the content of the teaching, while also having a good mastery of the research techniques. Going out in the role of an organizer in teaching on the basis of a problem situation, the teacher is intended to be more a leader and partner for students, and not a ready-made source of knowledge, its carrier and directive. During the preparation for problematic lessons in chemistry, the teacher:

- the fact that students intelligently perceive the situations they encounter as problematic and know how to put real learning issues on a special subject in front of the group, which students understand;
- coordinator of the entire process (solving tasks, putting the problem, solving, checking the result, etc.) carried out by students in chemistry and performing partner tasks for students;
- to try to involve students in the process of problem and its in-depth research, to motivate creative thinking readers with the help of masterfully posed questions;
- the teacher must acquire experiences such as being patient and tolerant by offering his help to the mistakes that students make in their efforts to find personal solutions, or in times when students are unsure in their search for a solution, sending them to the necessary sources of information.

We will give a few examples of problem situations in chemistry below:

The first problematic situation: let's take the fly familiar to all of us. The male of this insect secretes the substance muscalur (alkene) from himself in order to focus his female on himself. When the same substance is exposed to bromine water $C_{23}H_{46}Br_2$ forms a compound. If the substance is ozonized C_8H_7COH and $C_{13}H_{27}COH$ to divide. Solve the situation: how do you represent the structure formula of the alkene that the house fly separates from itself. Situation solution: $CH_3-(CH_2)-CH=CH-(CH_2)_{12}-CH_3$

The second problematic situation: Have you ever heard of the destruction of the Scott expedition in history. Scott and members of his expedition jumped to the pole for the purpose of the expedition. The expedition took out fuels in special containers made of metal. In a long-standing expedition, at a low temperature, the vessel broke and its fuel spilled. As a result, members of the expedition were killed. How could this have happened? Situation solution: yes. Scott expedition crash is known to us from history. The members of this expedition were made up of 40 people. Expedition fuels that jumped to the pole were stored in a jar, which was quarried with the help of tin. At a low temperature, the container broke and the fuel spilled. As a result, members of the expedition were killed.

The third problematic situation: the pheromone (causative agent) of leaf-cutting ants is the citral substance (geranial, neral). The smell of this substance is reminiscent of the smell of lemon. The fighting of the ants that smell it increases, scraping away all living things in the place where the smell comes out. 2,3,6,7-tetrabromo combined with citral bromine water-3,7-dimethyl forms octanal. Task: determine the name of the same article by international nomenclature. Situation solution: 3,7-dimethylactadiene -2,6-al. Citral $C_{10}H_{16}O$

composed of a mixture of CIS and trans forms, it is used in obtaining flavorings and vitamin A. Fourth problematic situation: German Alchemist discoverer and physician Iogan Ioaxim Bexer H_2SO_4 while experimenting with, boiling sulfuric acid is mistakenly released by ethyl alcohol over it. The Arashma was whipped and a more active combustible gas substance began to be released from methane gas. Assignment: How did Johann Ioachim Bexer name this gas, what reaction was carried out as a result of the experiment?

The fifth problematic situation: one day after a long conversation with his friends, Mendeleev said that he could collect tobacco smoke in the air in an empty jar without any difficulty in order to have some fun. Then, when his friend Repin papiros smokes and releases tobacco smoke into the air, he covers the mouth of an empty jar on the table with a glass plate. With a little time, a miracle happened, and an empty closed jar was filled with white "tobacco smoke". Then Mendeleev offers his friend Repin to smell. As soon as Repin, without believing, sniffs the smoke in the container, he quickly takes himself out of the container and begins to cough strongly.

Assignment: comment on what experience Mendeleev carried out?

Hence, these and similar life problem situations are formulated by the teacher based on the topic and develop the competence of students in the course of the lesson.

Problem-based teaching arms students with the methods of knowing the existence that surrounds them, develops skills and abilities to observe them purposefully, educates the skills of generalizing and summarizing the basic laws by substantiating them, instilling in them an interest in a possible research work.

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